

Assessing air pollution in European cities to support a citizen centered approach to air quality management

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Abstract

European cities have made significant progress over the last decades towards clean air. Despite this progress, several cities are still facing acute air pollution episodes, with various urban areas frequently exceeding air quality levels allowed by the European legal standards and WHO guidelines. In this paper, six European cities/ regions (Bristol, UK; Amsterdam, NL; Sosnowiec, PL; Ljubljana, SI; Aveiro, PT; Liguria, IT) are studied in terms of air quality, namely particulate matter, nitrogen dioxide and ozone. The concentrations trends from 2008 – 2017 in the different typology of monitoring stations are addressed, together with the knowledge of daily, weekly and seasonal pollution patterns to better understand the city specific profiles and to characterise pollutant dynamics and variations in multiple locations. Additionally, an analysis of the duration and severity of air pollution episodes is also discussed, followed by an analysis of the fulfillment of the legislated limit values.

Each of our 6 case study locations face different air pollution problems, but all these case studies have made some progress in reducing ambient concentrations. In Bristol, there have been strong downward trends in many air pollutants, but the levels of NO₂ remain persistently high and of concern. In recent years, decreasing concentration levels point to some success of Amsterdam air quality policies. PM₁₀ exceedances are a seasonal pollution problem in Ljubljana, Sosnowiec and Aveiro region (even if with different lev-

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els of severity). While, exceedances of NO₂ and O₃ concentrations are still problematic in Liguria region.

The main findings of this paper are particular relevant to define and compare future citizen-led strategies and policy initiatives that may be implemented to improve and fulfill the EU legislation and the WHO guidelines.

Keywords: European cities, EU legislation, ClairCity project, air quality, monitoring data, temporal patterns and trends

1. Introduction

Many European cities are affected by poor air quality levels and regularly exceed both the European standards prescribed by the Ambient Air Quality Directive (AQD) (2008/50/CE) and guidelines recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) (EEA, 2019, 2020). This is particularly the case for particulate matter with diameters of 10 μm and smaller (PM₁₀), for which both the daily and the yearly average limit values are often exceeded in many European cities (EEA, 2019, 2020). For fine inhalable particles (PM_{2.5}), the EU limit value is generally met (EEA, 2019, 2020), but only a few cities manage to keep concentrations below the levels recommended by the WHO (EEA, 2020; Thunis et al., 2018). According to the latest report released by the European Environment Agency (EEA) on air quality in Europe, the WHO guideline for PM_{2.5} annual mean was exceeded at 70% of the monitoring stations across Europe (EEA, 2020). Additionally, the EEA estimates that in 2018 nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) was linked to 54,000 premature deaths, and ground-level ozone was linked to 19,400 premature deaths across the European Union countries (EEA, 2020). Consequently, poor air quality is recognized as one of the most pressing environmental issues in urban areas and remains the largest environmental risk in Europe. More than an environmental issue, air pollution has become the world's largest environmental health threat (Lelieveld et al., 2020).

To reduce these air pollution effects, particularly in cities where most of the European population lives, it is important to define effective planning strategies for air quality improvement (Miranda et al., 2015; Monteiro et al., 2018b; Pisoni et al., 2019a; Viana et al., 2020). The 2008 European AQD requires Member States to design appropriate air quality plans for zones where the air quality does not comply with the AQD limit values, to plan

28 and implement possible emission reduction measures to improve air quality
29 (Coelho et al., 2020; Pisoni et al., 2019b; Thunis et al., 2016).

30 ClairCity, an innovative European project funded by the EU Horizon
31 2020 program (Ref: 689289), engaged thousands of citizens across Europe
32 to define policy measures that consider the optimal local interventions that
33 are more citizen centered in their design to achieve a low carbon, clean air,
34 health future. The project focussed on six distinct European urban areas, all
35 of them with over 50,000 inhabitants: Bristol in the United Kingdom, Ams-
36 terdam in the Netherlands, Ljubljana in Slovenia, Sosnowiec in Poland, the
37 Aveiro region in Portugal and the Liguria region around Genoa in Italy. The
38 focus of the project was to take a more citizen-centered approach to air qual-
39 ity management by primarily focusing on the relationships between citizens
40 day to day behaviors, practices and activities and the links to air pollution
41 and carbon emissions (Hayes, 2017). The current air quality management
42 practices need to go beyond the traditional approach to provide a new per-
43 spective based instead on citizens daily activities behaviour and practices
44 which will clearly allow the connection to be made between pollution and
45 behaviour, and link these to the various practices that constitute everyday
46 life within our cities. Therefore, the research question addressed in this paper
47 is: would it be possible to support air quality management practices with a
48 citizen-centered approach through a historical air quality assessment study?
49 To understand the local context, a complete diagnosis of the air quality and
50 its main emission sources for each case study was implemented. The main
51 objective of this paper is to present a comprehensive air quality assessment,
52 based on existing air quality monitoring data, to support a citizen centered
53 approach. The main findings of this paper will allow the identification of the
54 main problems and causes of air pollution, to then support the development
55 of more effective local policies for emission abatement in European cities by
56 initiating new modes of engaging citizens, stakeholders and policy makers.

57 In this paper, air quality data recorded in these different European cities
58 was analysed for a 10-year period (where available), focusing on the main
59 critical pollutants in urban areas, combining different approaches (Flemming
60 et al., 2005; Gama et al., 2018; Henschel et al., 2013; Jo and Park, 2005;
61 Liu et al., 2015; Lonati et al., 2006; Zhao et al., 2009). The paper is or-
62 ganised as follows: in Section 2, the air quality data collection methodology
63 along the six cities is described in detail, followed by a description of the
64 six urban case studies main characteristics. Section 3 focuses on the analy-
65 sis and interpretation of the monitoring data, considering the daily, weekly

66 and seasonal pollution patterns (sub-section 3.1), the concentrations trends
67 in the different typology of monitoring stations (sub-section 3.2), and the
68 duration and severity of air pollution episodes (sub-section 3.3). In addition,
69 an analysis of the fulfilment of the legislated limit values is presented as Sup-
70plementary Material (SM 5.2). Finally, in Section 4, the main conclusions
71 are summarized.

72 **2. Air quality assessment framework**

73 An assessment of measured ambient air quality data was performed for
74 the period from 2008 to 2017, focusing on PM_{10} , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, NO_2 and O_3 concen-
75trations (where available). The selection of ozone for this analysis, even if it
76 is not directly related with citizens behaviour, is justified by its health-related
77 effects, and assuming that a citizen-centered approach is not just about the
78 generation of pollution but also about the protection of health through expo-
79sure minimization. The main findings of this assessment support the baseline
80 characterization of the air quality status of the six cities and regions and will
81 be the basis for the validation of the air quality modelling tools applied in the
82 ClairCity project. The air quality assessment was performed for the study
83 areas included in the computational domains, shown in Figure 1, and cover
84 the urban areas of each case study and were selected based on a preliminary
85 discussion with local stakeholders.

86 *2.1. Air quality assessment methodology*

87 The air quality monitoring data was retrieved from the European Air
88 Quality Database (EEA, b) for the years 2008 to 2012, and from the Air
89 Quality e-Reporting database (EEA, a) for the years 2013 to 2017, for all
90 the case studies. Additionally, for Bristol data was obtained from the UK
91 Automatic Urban and Rural Network (AURN), which is part of the national
92 monitoring network and five additional monitoring stations maintained by
93 Bristol City Council. These monitoring stations follow the same QA/QC
94 procedures as the national AURN network.

95 The monitoring stations were selected based on their data capture for each
96 year. A station was considered eligible when half of the years (at least 5 out
97 of 10) had more than 75% data capture. An exception was made for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
98 in the Liguria Region station IT0858A, where only 4 years out of 10 were
99 available, otherwise there would be no data for this pollutant. Preference
100 was given of stations that have more recent data, meaning if a station fulfils

101 the criteria, but does not have data for any of the five more recent years it
102 was not selected. A list of all selected stations is presented in Table 1. In
103 Ljubljana, Sosnowiec and Liguria region some stations do not have hourly
104 PM data. In addition, all the selected monitoring stations are automatic and
105 use the chemiluminescence method to measure NO_2 concentrations, and the
106 ultraviolet (UV) photometry method to measure O_3 concentrations. While
107 different methods are used to measure PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations, the
108 tapered element oscillating microbalance (TEOM), the gravimetric analysis
109 and the beta ray attenuation, depending on the country and site. Data
110 measured using the TEOM or the beta ray attenuation method cannot always
111 be considered equivalent to the manual gravimetric reference method, which
112 is required in Europe for compliance measurements. Correction procedures
113 are employed by each Member State to obtain reference equivalent PM_{10} and
114 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ data series from automatic TEOM and beta-attenuation monitors.

115 Although all cities meet the monitoring requirements established by the
116 AQD, Amsterdam is clearly the city with the highest density air quality mon-
117 itoring network, with 17 air quality monitoring stations (AQS), distributed
118 over an area of 500 km^2 , and encompassing a population of 834,713 inhab-
119 itants. The assessment of the spatial representativeness (SR) of air quality
120 monitoring stations is an important subject linked with several research and
121 management areas, including risk assessment and population exposure, the
122 design of monitoring networks, model development, model evaluation and
123 data assimilation. The European Commission is working on the implemen-
124 tation of a harmonised programme for the monitoring of air pollutants and
125 to ensure that the information collected on air pollution is sufficiently rep-
126 resentative and comparable across the Community. However, there is not
127 yet detailed provisions on the methods for assessing the SR (Kracht et al.,
128 2017). Also in the scientific literature, there is no unified agreement to ad-
129 dress this complex problem, and no well-established procedure for assessing
130 SR has been identified so far. All the monitoring stations included in this
131 study follow the EU directive classification scheme based on two indicators
132 on different scales (Decision 2011/850/EU): “type of area” (rural, suburban,
133 urban), and “type of station” (in relation to predominant emission sources
134 relevant for the measurement: background, traffic, industrial). Concentra-
135 tions measured at background stations are assumed to be representative of
136 a wider area (EU, 2008), referring to “exposure of the general population”.
137 While the selected traffic and industrial stations in this study are not rep-
138 resentative of the “exposure of the general population”. Nevertheless, and

139 having in mind the main goal of the paper, which focuses on the relation-
140 ship between citizens behavior and air quality management, it is crucial to
141 consider all the stations within the boundaries of the city/ region.

142 This study employed classic statistical methods for time series analy-
143 sis by using the R package OpenAir (Carslaw and Ropkins, 2012; Ropkins
144 and Carslaw, 2012), developed for the purpose of analyzing air quality data.
145 Concentrations of PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, NO_2 , and O_3 registered at the six cities
146 were used to characterize the variability of mean pollutant concentrations
147 on the timescales from diurnal to annual, addressing the processes driving
148 this variability. In addition, long-term temporal trends of mean pollutant
149 concentrations have been estimated. To characterize extreme values in air
150 pollutant concentrations, the duration and severity of air pollution episodes
151 were also assessed in this study.

152 Furthermore, this analysis also integrated some field-knowledge from the
153 ClairCity engagement activities, namely local interviews with citizens, stake-
154 holders, decision- and policy-makers, which were crucial to identify the most
155 critical air pollution problems of each pilot city/ region, and the public per-
156 ception of those problems. All the collected data are compiled in Artola
157 and Bolscher (2018); Slingerland et al. (2018a, 2017); Slingerland and Smith
158 (2018); Slingerland et al. (2018b); Smith et al. (2017).

159 These approaches contribute to the historical air quality assessment study,
160 providing essential data to inform and engage citizens.

161 *2.2. Summary of the six EU case studies*

162 No two cities are the same, so the six EU case studies were chosen to
163 represent diversity such as different air pollution sources, geographies, me-
164 teorology, economies, demographics, and local air quality capacity and ca-
165 pabilities. Table 2 provides a summary of each case study city and region.
166 Further information can be found as Supplementary Material (SM5.1). Fig-
167 ure 1 shows the location of the AQS considered for each case study and the
168 corresponding classification.

Table 1: Summary of the air quality monitoring network of the case studies.

Case study	Type of stations	Number of stations measuring			
		PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	NO ₂	O ₃
Bristol	2 urban background	1	1	2	1
	4 urban traffic	–	–	4	–
Amsterdam	6 urban background	2	2	4	2
	6 urban traffic	4	3	5	1
	2 urban industrial	2	1	1	–
	3 rural background	3	2	1	–
Ljubljana	2 urban background	2	1	1	1
Sosnowiec	1 urban background	1	–	1	–
	1 urban traffic	1	1	1	–
Aveiro region	1 urban traffic	1	–	1	–
	1 suburban background	1	–	1	1
	1 suburban industrial	1	1	1	1
Liguria region	3 urban background	1	1	2	3
	5 urban traffic	–	–	5	–
	1 urban industrial	1	–	1	–

Table 2: Summary of the main characteristics of each case study (information was gathered from Artola and Bolscher (2018); Slingerland et al. (2018a, 2017); Slingerland and Smith (2018); Slingerland et al. (2018b); Smith et al. (2017)).

	Bristol	Amsterdam	Ljuljana	Sosnowiec	Aveiro region	Liguria region
Population ¹	450,000	834,713	288,919	206,000	363,752	855,834
Population density (hab/km ²)	4,000	4,700	1,075	2,376	215	466
Climate classification ²	Temperate Oceanic (Cbf)	Temperate Oceanic (Cbf)	Warm–summer humid continental (Dfb)	Warm–summer humid continental (Dfb)	Warm–summer mediterranean (Csb)	Hot–summer mediterranean (Csa)
Domain area	20 km × 20 km	25 km × 20 km	20 km × 20 km	20 km × 20 km	40 km × 55 km	25 km × 15 km
Main economic activities	Services Industry Higher-education	Port Airport Tourism Industry Services	Limited industry Services Tourism	Heavy industry Services	Heavy industry Port Services Agriculture (inland)	Services (mainly tourism) Industry Port
Population distribution within the area	Mainly central	Mainly central	Mainly central	More equally distributed	Mainly coastal	Mainly coastal
Number of stations per 100,000 inhabitants	1.3	2.0	0.7	1.0	0.8	1.1

¹data from 2016

²classified following the Köppen-Geiger Climate Classification System

Figure 1: Location of the air quality monitoring stations within the selected study areas of each case study: Bristol (a), Amsterdam (b), Ljubljana (c), Sosnowiec (d), Aveiro region (e), and Liguria region (f)

170 3. Air quality assessment

171 The results of the air quality assessment are presented in this section
172 considering the variability of pollutant concentrations on the timescales from
173 diurnal to annual (sub-section 3.1), the trend describing the mean concen-
174 trations evolution during the 10 years period (sub-section 3.2), and the du-
175 ration and severity of air pollution episodes (sub-section 3.3). In addition,
176 an analysis of the fulfillment of the legislated limit values is presented as
177 Supplementary Material (SM 5.2).

178 3.1. Time profiles

179 To characterize the air quality temporal patterns at the six case studies,
180 air quality observations have been grouped considering different time scales.
181 For each pollutant, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and O₃, hourly (mean hour of day
182 variation), daily (day of the week variation), and monthly (monthly plot)
183 cycle plots have been done, using the OpenAir package for R (Carslaw and
184 Ropkins, 2012; Ropkins and Carslaw, 2012). In these plots the mean and
185 the 95% confidence interval are depicted and the color of each line/shadow
186 represents the type of station: blue for the urban background; green for
187 the suburban background; yellow for the urban traffic; grey for the urban
188 industrial and orange for the rural background.

189 3.1.1. PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations

190 Figures 2 and 3 show the variation of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations,
191 respectively, by hour of the day, by day of the week and by month of the year,
192 considering all data observed between 2008 and 2017, for each case study.

193 Bristol, Amsterdam, Ljubljana, and Liguria hourly profiles show a peak
194 of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations in the morning (between 7 and 10h),
195 which may be linked with road traffic emissions. For Bristol, Ljubljana and
196 Sosnowiec, a similar peak is also observed in the evening. High PM₁₀ and
197 PM_{2.5} concentrations are also observed during night-time in Sosnowiec and
198 Aveiro region, that may be related with both the daily evolution of the
199 urban atmospheric boundary layer, which gets thinner during the night (Oke
200 et al., 2017), and with a contribution of semi-volatile material condensing on
201 ambient particles with the lower night-time temperatures (Harrison et al.,
202 2012). In turn, Liguria shows a strong decrease of PM concentrations in the
203 evening, an opposite pattern to the observed in the other cities. This may be
204 explained by the penetration of sea breezes in the evening, bringing cleaner

205 air into the city (e.g. Viana et al. (2005) found minimum PM levels during
206 night-time due to reductions on the average mixing height and night-time
207 catabatic winds, for a regional background site in the Barcelona city area).

208 Regarding the daily profiles, there is a negligible variability in Bristol for
209 both PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations, while in Amsterdam the profile indi-
210 cates a decrease of PM concentrations during weekends, more notably at the
211 traffic stations. During Sundays, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations are about
212 3.1 and 1.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively, lower than average weekdays concentration,
213 which reflects the importance of coarse particles of anthropogenic origin in
214 Amsterdam. For Sosnowiec the decrease of concentrations in weekends it
215 is not so evident. In Aveiro region, the daily profiles indicate slightly lower
216 concentrations on Sundays. Additionally, the traffic station monitored higher
217 concentrations (about 6.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) than the suburban background station,
218 which may be used as an estimation for the traffic contribution to PM₁₀ and
219 PM_{2.5} concentrations (Pant and Harrison, 2013). In addition, for Liguria,
220 the daily profile shows a decrease of PM₁₀ concentrations during the week-
221 end at the industrial station (about 3.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ lower on Sundays than during
222 average weekdays), while the background station profiles kept constant.

223 On contrary to the other cities/ regions, Liguria region monthly profile
224 shows peaks of PM concentrations during summer months, particularly for
225 PM_{2.5}. This may be linked with the enhancement of photochemically driven
226 secondary formation of aerosols, from anthropogenic precursors transported
227 from populated and industrialized areas such as the Po Valley.

228 In turn, Bristol and Amsterdam indicates a slight decrease of PM₁₀ and
229 PM_{2.5} concentrations in spring and summer months, with slightly higher lev-
230 els in winter months potentially linked with residential heating practices.
231 For Ljubljana, Aveiro, and particularly in Sosnowiec, monitored PM₁₀ and
232 PM_{2.5} concentrations are much higher during winter months than during
233 summer months, and are also higher than in the other cities. For exam-
234 ple, in Sosnowiec, mean winter concentrations are about 2.6 times higher
235 than those in the summer period. These results are in accordance with the
236 great seasonal variability of the PM_{2.5} concentrations in Poland described by
237 Rogula-Kozłowska et al. (2014). In this study, this variability is attributed
238 to the seasonal fluctuations of the emissions of PM and its precursors from
239 hard and brown coal combustion for energy production, growing in a heating
240 season, reaching maximum in winter, and decreasing in a non-heating period.

Figure 2: Hourly, daily, and monthly variability of the PM₁₀ concentrations observed between 2008 and 2017, for the 6 case studies. The solid line shows mean concentrations, while the bars in the daily and monthly plots, as well as the band in the hourly plots represent the 95% confidence intervals in the mean. Data from urban background stations is depicted in blue, suburban background in green, urban traffic in yellow, urban industrial in grey and rural background in orange.

Figure 3: Hourly, daily, and monthly variability of the PM_{2.5} concentrations observed between 2008 and 2017, for the 6 case studies. The solid line shows mean concentrations, while the bars in the daily and monthly plots, as well as the band in the hourly plots represent the 95% confidence intervals in the mean. Data from urban background stations is depicted in blue, suburban background in green, urban traffic in yellow, urban industrial in grey and rural background in orange.

Figure 4: Hourly variability by season of the PM_{10} concentrations observed between 2008 and 2017, for Ljubljana (a), Sosnowiec (b) and Aveiro (c). The solid line shows mean concentrations while the shading shows the 95% confidence interval in the mean. Data from urban background stations is depicted in blue, suburban background in green, urban traffic in yellow and urban industrial in grey.

241 Moreover, during winter meteorological conditions which favour the accumu-
 242 lation of pollutants at surface levels are common, which may contribute to
 243 episodic increases in PM concentrations (Chen et al., 2020). To complement
 244 this analysis, Figure 4 presents the hourly variation of PM_{10} concentrations
 245 by season of the year, for the three cities/ regions. At Ljubljana, the PM_{10}
 246 daily profile has a similar progression between seasons. Conversely, Sos-
 247 nowiec and Aveiro exhibit a huge peak in mean hourly concentrations during
 248 late evening and night, during winter, but without significant peaks during
 249 summer. PM_{10} mean concentrations at 00h are 52.4 and 32.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ higher
 250 than during summer, at Sosnowiec and Aveiro, respectively. As previously
 251 stated, evening peaks may be related with daily evolution of the atmospheric
 252 boundary layer, evening contribution of domestic sources such as heating
 253 (Gonçalves et al., 2012; Vicente et al., 2015) and cooking, and contribution
 254 of semi-volatile material condensing on ambient particles (Harrison et al.,
 255 2012). All these causes are more important during winter (due to thinner
 256 and more stable boundary layers, more emissions from heating, and colder
 257 night-time temperatures), which may explain the results shown on Figure 4.

258 Sosnowiec also has large smog problems in wintertime. According to the
 259 literature (Adamczyk et al., 2017; Lubecki et al., 2019; Woźniak et al., 2020),
 260 the main sources of particulate matter are low stack emissions from household
 261 stoves burning coal and waste. Episodes of high concentrations of PM are
 262 most often associated with increased dust emissions from communal-living
 263 sources, which is accompanied by unfavorable conditions of air pollution

264 spread (anticyclones situations with a large territorial range, weak wind,
265 strong thermal inversion, negative average daily air temperatures).

266 Previous studies for the northern and central part of Portugal, Aveiro
267 Region included, indicate that, overall, residential and commercial combus-
268 tion units for heating, followed by industrial combustion processes, are the
269 main source of PM₁₀ (Borrego et al., 2010; Figueiredo et al., 2013; Gonçalves
270 et al., 2012; Lopes, 2018; Monteiro et al., 2018a).

271 3.1.2. NO₂ and O₃ concentrations

272 The temporal variability of NO₂ and O₃ concentrations in the troposphere
273 is connected, since these two pollutants are both involved in several specific
274 chemical reactions which play a key role in their concentrations. Typically,
275 the diurnal cycle of O₃ and NO₂ exhibit an inverse relationship where O₃
276 shows a peak during the afternoon (due to photochemical production) and
277 lower night-time concentrations. Close to emission sources, freshly emitted
278 NO locally scavenges O₃, yielding NO₂, which contributes to the night-time
279 drop in O₃ concentrations. In addition, dry deposition of O₃ plays also an
280 important role in the decrease of the concentrations of this pollutant during
281 the night and early morning. In terms of monthly profiles, as sunlight triggers
282 OH production, causing NO₂ to be removed from the atmosphere (Melkonyan
283 and Kuttler, 2012), lower NO₂ concentrations are expected during summer.
284 On the other hand, higher values of NO₂ are expected in winter, when the so-
285 lar activity and OH concentrations are lower (Melkonyan and Kuttler, 2012).
286 Moreover, winter is the season with the strongest anthropogenic emissions in
287 Europe because of heating (Cincinelli et al., 2019; Vicente and Alves, 2018).

288 Figures 5 and 6 show the time variation of NO₂ and O₃ concentrations,
289 respectively, considering all data observed between 2008 and 2017. Note
290 that for O₃ only 5 case studies were considered, due to the lack of data for
291 Sosnowiec.

292 The hourly profiles of NO₂ concentrations in the six cities/ regions show
293 two peaks of concentrations, one in the morning, and the other in the evening,
294 associated with the peak road traffic in the cities. In general, traffic stations
295 (data plotted in yellow) show the largest NO₂ concentrations. This behavior
296 was expected, since NO₂ in ambient air is in large part derived from the
297 oxidation of NO, a pollutant which is emitted from combustion processes.

Figure 5: Hourly, daily, and monthly variability of the NO₂ concentrations observed between 2008 and 2017, for the 6 case studies. The solid line shows mean concentrations, while the bars in the daily and monthly plots, as well as the band in the hourly plots represent the 95% confidence intervals in the mean. Data from urban background stations is depicted in blue, suburban background in green, urban traffic in yellow, urban industrial in grey and rural background in orange.

Figure 6: Hourly, daily, and monthly variability of the O_3 concentrations observed between 2008 and 2017, for the 6 case studies. The solid line shows mean concentrations, while the bars in the daily and monthly plots, as well as the band in the hourly plots represent the 95% confidence intervals in the mean. Data from urban background stations is depicted in blue, suburban background in green, urban traffic in yellow and urban industrial in grey.

298 Since NO sources, at urban areas, are mainly from vehicular exhaust, NO₂
299 is therefore a clear indicator for road traffic (Rafael et al., 2020). One traffic
300 station is highlighted in Bristol, as having very high mean NO₂ concentra-
301 tions between 9h and 18h (higher than 110 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Although the NO₂
302 concentrations observed in this station present lower values during the week-
303 end, due to lower traffic levels and less pronounced peaks (mean difference
304 between week days and Sundays is about 23.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, very high mean levels
305 are registered even on Sundays (higher than 50 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).

306 In Ljubljana, cars are the most used means of transportation, which
307 causes problems of traffic congestion (Slingerland et al., 2018b). Although
308 the city’s air quality monitoring network does not include traffic stations (see
309 Table 1), the observed NO₂ cycles at background stations still denote traffic
310 influence, with peaks at rush hours.

311 Sosnowiec faces typical urban congestion problems, which explain the
312 higher NO₂ concentrations at the traffic station than at the background sta-
313 tion (with a mean delta of about 28.5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).

314 In the Aveiro region, a contribution of 64% from traffic emissions for the
315 NO₂ concentrations was found (Gama et al., 2021).

316 Liguria also shows significantly higher concentrations at the traffic sta-
317 tions, when compared to the background stations (mean difference between
318 traffic and background stations is about 18.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The industrial sta-
319 tion in this city also shows NO₂ peaks in the morning and evening and mean
320 concentrations during daytime of the same levels as the monitored range at
321 the traffic stations. However, during nighttime, the NO₂ concentrations are
322 higher at the industrial station than at traffic stations, denoting that the
323 industrial facilities operate during the entire day.

324 As expected, since NO₂ is converted to O₃ in a reaction catalyzed by sun-
325 light (UV radiation), NO₂ (Figure 5) and O₃ (Figure 6) hourly profiles show
326 an inverse relationship. O₃ concentrations peak is found in the early after-
327 noon (between 1 and 4 pm), typically associated with local production of O₃
328 which reaches maximum levels with the highest solar radiation. O₃ concen-
329 trations start to decrease in the evening with the absence of sunlight, when
330 the ozone production ceases, and the loss processes dominate. Minimum
331 mean concentrations are reached around 6 - 9 am (due to O₃ scavenging by
332 NO, during morning rush hours), and then start to increase, reaching their
333 maximum in the afternoon, around 2 pm. The hourly peak in O₃ mean
334 concentrations is the highest in Liguria (75.8 - 89.5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), followed by
335 Aveiro (71.5 - 73.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and Ljubljana (69.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Liguria region

336 shows indeed mean O_3 concentrations higher than the other case studies.
337 This finding is particularly relevant during the nighttime period, when mean
338 observed concentrations in Liguria are in the range 60 - 80 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ while in
339 other regions are lower than 40 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

340 In general, the NO_2 weekly profiles of all the monitoring stations of all
341 case studies, show lower concentrations during the weekend. These find-
342 ing highlight that, as expected over urban areas, the air quality is marked
343 by anthropogenic cycles. On contrary, O_3 concentrations are higher during
344 weekends. This corresponds to the so-called weekend effect (Sicard et al.,
345 2020). High concentrations of freshly emitted NO locally scavenge O_3 , a pro-
346 cess leading to formation of NO_2 . Close to the sources this titration process
347 can be considered as an ozone sink. In addition, high NO_2 concentrations de-
348 flect the initial oxidation step of VOCs by forming other products (e.g. nitric
349 acid), which prevents the net formation of O_3 . Because of these reactions, a
350 decrease in NO_x can lead to an increase in O_3 at low VOC/ NO_x ratios, as is
351 the case in cities. In this often-called VOC-limited regime, emission control
352 of organic compounds is more efficient to reduce peak values of ozone pollu-
353 tion locally (Sicard et al., 2020). Due to the titration effect (reaction of O_3
354 with NO), lower O_3 are usually recorded by stations monitoring busy traffic
355 and this pollutant is commonly not measured at traffic stations. Amsterdam
356 network is an exception, with O_3 data at an air quality traffic station. As
357 expected, O_3 concentrations are lower (with a delta of 3.9 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, which
358 corresponds to 9%) at this site than at the urban background ones.

359 In all the six cities/ regions, seasonal profiles indicate higher NO_2 con-
360 centrations in winter months. As previously mentioned, this behaviour is
361 related, on the one hand, with the chemical reactions where NO_2 is involved
362 (as sunlight triggers OH production) and, on the other hand, with extra NO_x
363 emissions, during winter, from combustion processes for heating purposes.

364 Regarding the ozone seasonal profiles, higher mean concentrations are
365 recorded during spring, specifically in May in Bristol (60.9 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and
366 Amsterdam (62.5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), and in April and May in Aveiro region (61.7 μg
367 m^{-3}). The ozone spring maximum is a common characteristic of many mid-
368 latitudes regions in the northern hemisphere (Monks, 2000; Parrish et al.,
369 2021; Zara et al., 2021). The physical and chemical mechanisms behind
370 the spring maximum have been revised by Monks (2000) and Vingarzan
371 (2004) and include both enhanced photochemistry in the free troposphere
372 and stratospheric input. Indeed, O_3 concentrations in Europe are very much
373 influenced not only by local and regional production but also by northern

374 mid-latitudes background concentrations. From all the case studies, Aveiro,
 375 Bristol and Amsterdam are the ones located closer to the Atlantic. Their
 376 location and the dominant synoptic conditions, and the similarity of their
 377 spring mean concentrations (about $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) point out the relevance of the
 378 high background O_3 concentrations received from the Atlantic to the high
 379 mean concentrations observed in these regions during spring (Auvray and
 380 Bey, 2005).

381 In Ljubljana and Liguria, the highest O_3 mean concentrations are reg-
 382 istered from April to August/ September. During this period, mean O_3
 383 concentrations are higher than $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Ljubljana and higher than 80
 384 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Liguria. Although high mean concentrations are recorded dur-
 385 ing spring, the maximum mean concentrations occur in July and August in
 386 Ljubljana and Liguria, respectively. This behaviour indicates that in these
 387 regions, the observed O_3 concentrations have a strong contribution from local
 388 and/or regional ozone production, which is favoured by the summer higher
 389 atmospheric temperature leading to enhanced photochemical reactions and
 390 O_3 formation.

391 To complement our analysis on O_3 variability, Figure 7 presents the
 392 hourly variation of O_3 concentrations by season of the year, for the three
 393 cities/regions with the highest concentrations: Liguria, Aveiro and Ljubl-
 394 jana.

Figure 7: Hourly variability by season of the year of the O_3 concentrations observed between 2008 and 2017, for Ljubljana (a), Aveiro (b) and Liguria (c). The solid line shows mean concentrations while the shading shows the 95% confidence interval in the mean. Data from urban background stations is depicted in blue, suburban background in green and urban industrial in grey.

395 Ljubljana has a typical seasonal variation of the O_3 hourly profiles. Dur-
 396 ing winter, concentrations are more constant during the day (low diurnal

397 amplitude), and O₃ mean peaks achieve higher magnitude during autumn,
398 spring and summer. The mean difference between daily minimum and max-
399 imum O₃ concentrations is higher during summer (about 70 μg m⁻³) and
400 lower during winter (about 15 μg m⁻³). In Aveiro, this delta is similar
401 during spring and summer (about 45-50 μg m⁻³). However, as nighttime O₃
402 concentrations are lower during summer than during spring, the mean profile
403 of the summer season shows lower concentrations than during spring.

404 The seasonal variation of the O₃ hourly profiles in Liguria is quite inter-
405 esting. Observed concentrations during the nighttime period are in average
406 much higher than in the other case studies, for all the seasons. During win-
407 ter, the mean highest daily concentrations are recorded during the nighttime
408 period. Liguria is located on the north-west of Italy, in the Mediterranean
409 coast. Several studies have been published regarding the ozone concentra-
410 tions in the Mediterranean Basin, which are relatively high when compared
411 to other European areas (Cristofanelli and Bonasoni, 2009). In addition,
412 high O₃ values are typical not only for ground level measurements in the
413 Mediterranean, but in the entire boundary layer (Kalabokas et al., 2017).
414 The transport of polluted air masses from Europe and other continents to
415 southern Europe/ Mediterranean Basin, favours photochemical O₃ produc-
416 tion in a region frequently characterised by high solar radiation intensity
417 (Cristofanelli and Bonasoni, 2009). Within the Western Mediterranean area
418 and based on a cruise ship measurements between April and October for two
419 years, the Liguria region/ Gulf of Genoa was identified as one of the two
420 main ozone “hot spots” (Velchev et al., 2011). The main cause of high O₃
421 levels in the Gulf of Genoa during this period (between April and October)
422 was found to be outflow of polluted air from the Po Valley (with contribu-
423 tions also from the Genoa area) and, to a minor extent, from Marseille area
424 as well. During specific meteorological events, the vertical motion of strato-
425 spheric air into the lower troposphere may represent a non-negligible source
426 of background O₃. This stratosphere–troposphere exchange process exhibits
427 a strong seasonality with a maximum in winter and spring and a minimum
428 in summer (Sharma et al., 2017), and may partially explain the winter O₃
429 hourly profile plotted for Liguria (Figure 7).

430 3.2. Trend analysis

431 A trend analysis was performed to investigate the evolution registered and
432 expected to the future. Long-term temporal trends of pollutant concentra-
433 tions have been estimated with the TheilSen function of the OpenAir pack-

434 age for R (Carslaw and Ropkins, 2012), which quantifies monotonic trends
435 in unit/year, and calculates the associated p value through bootstrap simula-
436 tions. Trend is estimated for mean monthly values, and the 95% confidence
437 interval of the slope is presented (see Table 3). In this analysis, data has
438 been deseasonalized using the seasonal-trend decomposition procedure based
439 on locally weighted scatterplot smoothing LOESS (Cleveland et al., 1990).
440 The symbols shown next to each trend estimate relate to how statistically
441 significant the trend estimate is: $p < 0.001 = **$, $p < 0.01 = *$,
442 $p < 0.05 = *$ and $p < 0.1 = +$.

443 Overall all the cities and regions have made significant progress over the
444 last decade towards a clean air. This progress was mainly achieved due to
445 the implementation of effective air quality management policies nationally
446 and locally (e.g. the European legislation, such as air quality directive (EU,
447 2008)).

448 PM_{10} concentrations are decreasing in all the cities and regions where sta-
449 tistically significant trends were computed (Bristol, Amsterdam, Ljubljana,
450 Sosnowiec and Aveiro). Similarly, $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations are also decreasing,
451 despite the limited data available for the 10-years period, thus only Amster-
452 dam, Sosnowiec and Aveiro show statistically significant evolution trends for
453 this pollutant. Overall decreasing trends of PM concentrations may be asso-
454 ciated with emissions reductions from the residential sector, as well as from
455 industries. NO_2 concentrations are typically decreasing in all the case stud-
456 ies (exception for the background station in Aveiro). On contrary, O_3 mean
457 concentrations are increasing in Bristol, Amsterdam, Ljubljana and Liguria
458 region, but decreasing in Aveiro. NO_2 concentration trends are mostly as-
459 sociated with reductions on NO_x emissions from on-road transport. The
460 increasing O_3 trends reflect the trends in NO_2 concentrations.

Table 3: Trend analysis for the 6 case studies. Trend estimates represent the change of concentrations per year, as an average over the entire period (from 2008 to 2017) and are shown in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. The symbols shown next to each trend estimate relate to how statistically significant the trend estimate is: $p < 0.001 = ***, p < 0.01 = **, p < 0.05 = *$ and $p < 0.1 = +$. n.s.s. stands for not statistically significant.

Case study	Monitoring station (type)	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	NO ₂	O ₃
Bristol	GB00203 (UT)			-0.51 [-0.69, -0.37] ***	
Bristol	GB00215 (UT)			-1.27 [-1.79, -0.71] ***	
Bristol	GB00270 (UT)			-1.04 [-1.44, -0.72] ***	
Bristol	GB00318 (UT)			-2.89 [-3.76, -1.89] ***	
Bristol	GB00463 (UT)			-0.73 [-1.13, -0.32] ***	
Bristol	GB0884A (UB)	-0.57 [-0.81, -0.36] ***	n.s.s.	-0.81 [-1.11, -0.47] ***	0.52 [0.12, 0.89] **
Amsterdam	NL00002 (UT)			-1.61 [-1.94, -1.29] ***	
Amsterdam	NL00003 (UB)				0.90 [-0.06, 1.68] +
Amsterdam	NL00007 (UT)	-1.23 [-1.62, -0.79] ***	-0.82 [-1.35, -0.31] *	-2.02 [-2.48, -1.55] ***	
Amsterdam	NL00012 (UT)	-1.17 [-1.55, -0.78] ***	-0.67 [-1.09, -0.14] *	-1.64 [-1.96, -1.33] ***	0.61 [-0.04, 1.33] +
Amsterdam	NL00014 (UB)	-0.82 [-1.23, -0.50] ***	-1.05 [-1.72, -0.45] ***	-0.76 [-1.02, -0.56] ***	1.24 [0.47, 1.98] **
Amsterdam	NL00016 (UB)	n.s.s.	n.s.s.		
Amsterdam	NL00017 (UT)	-1.43 [-1.81, -1.00] ***	-1.11 [-1.75, -0.56] ***	-1.13 [-1.37, -0.90] ***	
Amsterdam	NL00019 (UB)			-0.56 [-0.80, -0.38] ***	
Amsterdam	NL00020 (UT)			-1.44 [-1.75, -1.12] ***	
Amsterdam	NL00021 (UB)			-0.54 [-0.74, -0.39] ***	
Amsterdam	NL00022 (UB)			-0.39 [-0.61, -0.19] ***	
Amsterdam	NL00545 (UT)	-0.84 [-1.17, -0.52] ***			
Amsterdam	NL00546 (UI)	-1.29 [-1.90, -0.66] ***			
Amsterdam	NL00561 (RB)	-0.79 [-1.24, -0.35] ***	-0.72 [-1.35, 0.06] +		
Amsterdam	NL00565 (RB)	-0.60 [-1.04, -0.23] ***			
Amsterdam	NL00703 (RB)	-0.91 [-1.27, -0.59] ***	-0.96 [-1.66, -0.25] *	-0.57 [-0.87, -0.30] ***	
Amsterdam	NL00704 (UI)	n.s.s.	-0.88 [-1.44, -0.24] *	n.s.s.	

Table 4: Trend analysis for the 6 case studies. Trend estimates represent the change of concentrations per year, as an average over the entire period (from 2008 to 2017) and are shown in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. The symbols shown next to each trend estimate relate to how statistically significant the trend estimate is: $p < 0.001 = \text{***}$, $p < 0.01 = \text{**}$, $p < 0.05 = \text{*}$ and $p < 0.1 = \text{+}$. n.s.s. stands for not statistically significant.

Case study	Monitoring station (type)	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	NO ₂	O ₃
Ljubljana	SI0003A (UB)	-0.76 [-1.08, -0.47] ***		-0.24 [-0.51, 0.05] +	0.50 [0.09, 0.81] *
Ljubljana	SI0058A (UB)	n.s.s.	n.s.s.		
Sosnowiec	PL0529A (UB)	-2.00 [-2.67, -1.37] ***		-2.20 [-3.29, -1.00] ***	
Sosnowiec	PL0567A (UT)	n.s.s.	-1.12 [-1.83, -0.17] **	n.s.s.	
Aveiro	PT02004 (SI)	-1.01 [-1.37, -0.65] ***	-0.70 [-0.98, -0.46] ***	-0.99 [-1.21, -0.77] ***	-0.91 [-1.47, -0.48] ***
Aveiro	PT02017 (UT)	-1.95 [-2.34, -1.56] ***		-0.59 [-0.87, -0.35] ***	
Aveiro	PT02018 (SB)	-0.57 [-0.86, -0.30] ***		0.30 [0.08, 0.57] *	-0.88 [-1.27, -0.48] ***
Liguria	IT0852A (UI)	n.s.s.		-1.59 [-2.36, -0.82] ***	
Liguria	IT0853A (UT)			n.s.s.	
Liguria	IT0854A (UB)	n.s.s.		-0.91 [-1.24, -0.50] ***	2.57 [1.51, 3.68] ***
Liguria	IT0856A (UB)				2.65 [1.78, 3.52] ***
Liguria	IT0858A (UB)		n.s.s.	-2.24 [-2.91, -1.51] ***	0.89 [0.28, 1.45] ***
Liguria	IT1698A (UT)			-1.63 [-2.37, -0.76] ***	
Liguria	IT1850A (UT)			-1.85 [-2.77, -0.81] ***	
Liguria	IT1884A (UT)			-2.15 [-2.91, -1.57] ***	
Liguria	IT1887A (UT)			-2.51 [-3.40, -1.56] ***	

463 These results are different from the trends estimated by Guerreiro et al.
464 (2014) for the 93.15 percentile of maximum daily 8-h mean concentrations
465 (as indicator for the EU target value for the protection of health), for the
466 period 2002 – 2011. In that study, although 80% of the European monitoring
467 stations did not reveal a clear trend, 18% registered a statistically significant
468 decreasing trend, and 2% registered a significant increasing trend, most of
469 them in the Iberian Peninsula (where Aveiro region is located). The differ-
470 ence in those results is probably related with the choice of the O₃ parameter
471 (93.15 percentile of maximum daily 8-h mean concentrations against mean
472 monthly concentrations) for the trend analysis.

473 The highest decreasing trends for the evolution of mean PM₁₀ concentra-
474 tions are estimated for Sosnowiec (-2.00 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}/\text{yr}$ at the urban background
475 PL0529A station) and Aveiro (-1.95 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}/\text{yr}$ at the urban traffic PT02017
476 station). Those two cities were highlighted in the previous section, due to
477 their high PM concentrations, in particular during winter late evening and
478 night-time period. In Sosnowiec, pollutant concentrations decreased over
479 the last decades, and according to Slingerland and Smith (2018) this was
480 due to closure and modernisation of industries after the political and eco-
481 nomic change of the 1990s. The main drivers of the observed reductions in
482 concentrations in Sosnowiec, most of which have been largely driven by EU
483 regulation, include cleaner power generation, lower increases in energy de-
484 mand per household due to more efficient housing and appliances, improved
485 road transport technologies and fuels, and reductions in industrial emissions
486 measures, particularly regarding transport. To address the problem of local
487 low-stack residential heating, subsidies for replacing the commonly used low-
488 efficiency household stoves and boilers have been introduced (Slingerland and
489 Smith, 2018). Decreasing trends in particulate matter concentrations over
490 Portugal had already been shown by Gama et al. (2018), using observations
491 from background air quality monitoring stations recorded from 2007 to 2016.
492 According to this study, the main factor contributing to the PM10 decrease
493 in urban areas is the decrease in the coarse PM (2.5-10 μm) concentrations.

494 The highest decreasing trends for the evolution of mean NO₂ concen-
495 trations are estimated for Bristol (-2.89 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}/\text{yr}$ at the BCC urban traffic
496 GB00318 station) and Liguria (-2.51 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}/\text{yr}$ at the urban traffic IT1887A
497 station).

498 In Bristol, the potential reasons behind those decreasing trends are the
499 local policies included in the air quality action plans because of the designa-
500 tion of parts of Bristol as an Air Quality Management Area. The measures

501 in the plan were almost entirely transport focused (Smith et al., 2017).

502 While, in Liguria region the downward trends have been the result of im-
503 plemented measures to reduce industry emissions (EU legislation and the de-
504 commissioning of plants), harbour emissions (standards for fuels), and trans-
505 port emissions (standards for diesel cars and traffic and mobility measures
506 related to improving the railway, the metro, the bus fleet, and fostering elec-
507 tric mobility). These measures have helped bring down NO₂ concentrations,
508 albeit not enough to comply with the EU limit values at all the traffic sta-
509 tions. The closing of different industrial plants, due to a lack of compliance
510 with the regulation on air pollutant emissions, is likely an influential factor
511 (Artola and Bolscher, 2018).

512 3.3. *Pollution episodes*

513 In the previous sections, air quality at the six case studies was character-
514 ized using averaged quantities. However, when assessing air quality, we are
515 often interested in the extremes of these quantities, e.g., the concentrations
516 of a given pollutant which may be harmful to the ecosystems and the human
517 health. Thus, in this section, we will look at these extremes, using the short-
518 term thresholds established in the European Air Quality Directive (Directive
519 2008/50/EC; (EU, 2008)) for the protection the human health. In addition,
520 a detailed analysis of the fulfillment of the legislated limit values was per-
521 formed for the six case studies and is available as Supplementary Material
522 (SM 5.2).

523 For each case study, the observed concentrations above the short-term
524 thresholds for the protection of the human health, defined for PM₁₀, NO₂,
525 and O₃ (Table 5), were used to assess the occurrence of pollution episodes,
526 and to characterize those episodes based on their magnitudes and duration.
527 In this study, an episode is defined as a period of consecutive days (for PM₁₀
528 and O₃) or hours (for NO₂) where a concentration above the threshold was
529 observed in at least one station of the case study air quality monitoring
530 network. This approach has however some limitations: for example, in a
531 week with concentrations above the threshold for a given pollutant, if there
532 is a day where no station recorded data, this period will be divided into two
533 separate episodes.

534 Between 2008 and 2017, all the six case studies recorded PM₁₀ concentra-
535 tions above the daily limit value for the protection of the human health (50
536 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Those exceedances occurred mainly from October to March (Figure
537 S3). However, in Bristol and Liguria region, although there are exceedances,

Table 5: Short-term limit values or target values established in the Directive 2008/50/EC for the protection of the human health for PM₁₀, NO₂, and O₃.

Pollutant	Time aggregation	Threshold ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
PM ₁₀	mean daily concentrations	50
NO ₂	hourly concentrations	200
O ₃	maximum daily eight-hour mean concentrations	120

538 the PM₁₀ daily mean limit value was not exceeded more than 35 days per
 539 year in any station and thus there is compliance with the EU legislation (see
 540 Supplementary Material for details).

541 The frequency distribution graphs of the duration of PM₁₀ episodes in
 542 days, for each case study, are presented in Figure 8. In this analysis, Am-
 543 sterdam, Ljubljana, Sosnowiec and Aveiro are highlighted as the case studies
 544 with a higher number of PM₁₀ episodes.

Figure 8: Characterization of the PM₁₀ episodes which took place from 2008 till 2017, for the 6 case studies.

545 Three case studies recorded pollution episodes with mean PM₁₀ concen-
546 trations above the limit value for the protection of the human health during
547 10 or more consecutive days: Sosnowiec (18 episodes), Ljubljana (3 episodes)
548 and Aveiro region (5 episodes). The complete list of episodes with a dura-
549 tion of 10 or more days among the 10-year period is given as Supplementary
550 Material (Table S1). Those episodes affected all type of monitoring stations
551 existent in those three case studies (e.g., urban traffic and background in
552 Sosnowiec, urban background in Ljubljana, and urban traffic, background
553 and industrial in Aveiro region).

554 Contrary to what happens, for example, in Aveiro region, where the most
555 persistent episodes were not recorded in the most recent years, in Sosnowiec
556 the most persistent episode (37 consecutive days with PM₁₀ exceedances),
557 which is also the one where one of the monitoring stations recorded its highest
558 value (306.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at PL0567A station), took place in the latest study year
559 (between 14 Jan and 19 Feb 2017). This evidence indicates that, despite
560 the observed reduction in particulate matter mean concentrations through
561 the study period ($-2.00 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}\text{yr}^{-1}$ for PM₁₀ at PL0529A, as presented in
562 Table 3), PM₁₀ continues to be a pollutant of great concern at Sosnowiec.
563 Another great PM₁₀ episode that affected this city occurred between 31 Jan
564 and 14 Feb 2012 (15 consecutive days with PM₁₀ exceedances), when the
565 values recorded in the PL0529A station reached 541 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

566 For NO₂, between 2008 and 2017, all the case studies but Ljubljana
567 recorded concentrations above the hourly limit value for the protection of
568 the human health (200 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Although Amsterdam and Sosnowiec did
569 not record more than the 18 NO₂ exceedances per year permitted in the AQD,
570 the annual limit value for this pollutant (40 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) was exceeded at specific
571 traffic stations during several years of the study period in these two case stud-
572 ies (see the Supplementary Material for details). Both Ljubljana and Aveiro
573 region are compliant with the two (annual and hourly) EU limit values for
574 the protection of the human health. Contrary to PM₁₀, NO₂ exceedances do
575 not show a marked seasonality (Figure S7).

576 The frequency distribution graphs of the duration of NO₂ episodes in
577 hours, for each case study, are presented in Figure 9. Bristol is highlighted
578 in this analysis due to the high number of NO₂ episodes, 2 of them which
579 persisted for 12 hours, and another one for 10 hours.

580 Two case studies recorded pollution episodes with mean NO₂ concentra-
581 tions above the limit value for the protection of the human health during
582 5 or more consecutive hours: Bristol (19 episodes) and Liguria region (2

Figure 9: Characterization of the NO₂ episodes which took place from 2008 till 2017, for the 6 case studies.

583 episodes). The complete list of episodes with a duration of 5 or more hours
 584 among the 10-year period is given as Supplementary Material (Table S2).

585 During the two episodes highlighted in the Liguria region, which occurred
 586 in 20 Dec 2009 and 3 Dec 2012, exceedances have been recorded in one traffic
 587 station only. At Bristol, from the 19 episodes with 5 or more consecutive
 588 hours of exceedances, only one (2 June 2008) is associated with exceedances
 589 in more than one station. From those 19 episodes, which were registered
 590 in traffic stations, the ones which occur between 17 and 19 Mar 2009 and
 591 between 26 and 29 Aug 2015 can be considered exceptionally persistent, not
 592 only because of the number of hours with concentrations above $40 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$,
 593 but also because they occur during consecutive days.

594 All the five case studies with O₃ data recorded days with eight-hour mean
 595 concentrations higher than $120 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during the study period. However,
 596 Bristol and Amsterdam present a low number of exceedances per year, show-
 597 ing compliance with the EU legislation. As expected, O₃ exceedances to the
 598 target value for the protection of the human health show a marked season-

599 ality, with a higher number of exceedances from April to September (Figure
 600 S9). Although some case studies presented mean maximum concentrations
 601 during spring (e.g., Aveiro, Amsterdam and Bristol, see Figure 6), the max-
 602 imum number of exceedances is observed during summer in all case studies.

603 For O_3 , frequency distribution graphs of the duration of pollution episodes
 604 in days, are presented in Figure 10. Only the Liguria region recorded pollu-
 605 tion episodes with maximum daily eight-hour mean concentrations above the
 606 target value for the protection of the human health during 10 or more con-
 607 secutive days. In this region, 26 of these long-lasting episodes were recorded
 608 among the 10-year period, distributed within the study period (Table S3).
 609 An exceptional episode occurred from 20 Jun to 17 Sep 2016, when O_3 re-
 610 mained higher than $120 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during 90 consecutive days. This episode
 611 was exceptional not only because of its persistence, but also regarding the
 612 observed concentrations: the three urban background monitoring stations
 613 that measure O_3 recorded the maximum concentrations (206.0, 245.0 and
 614 $216.0 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) over the study period within this episode.

Figure 10: Characterization of the O_3 episodes which took place from 2008 till 2017, for the 5 case studies.

615 *3.4. Summary analysis*

616 To evaluate the air quality status of each case study, a set of criteria were
 617 established aiming to classify an air pollutant as indicator of historical air
 618 pollution issues. Table 6 summarizes the cities/ regions per pollutant and per
 619 type of station. The following criteria were established for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and
 620 NO₂ concentrations: i) the annual mean concentrations above the yearly EU
 621 limit value in any station, and in at least two years (YR); ii) and/ or a number
 622 of exceedances registered above the allowed per year, in any station, and in
 623 at least two years (HD). The criteria established for O₃ concentrations is the
 624 number of exceedances registered for O₃ target value over the allowed per
 625 year (HD). Additionally, the occurrence of exceptionally persistent pollution
 626 episodes of PM₁₀, NO₂, and O₃ concentrations were also considered as an
 627 indicator (PE), using the criteria mentioned in sub-section 3.3 (e.g., episodes
 628 are classified as persistent when lasting for 10 or more consecutive days in
 629 the case of PM₁₀ and O₃, and for 5 or more consecutive hours in the case of
 630 NO₂).

Table 6: Summary of the main air pollution problems identified for each case study and split by type of station, for the 10-years period. HD points out a problem of hourly or daily exceedances, YR represents a problem with exceedances to the annual mean limit value, and PE indicates the existence of persistent episodes.

	Type of station	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	NO ₂	O ₃
Bristol	traffic			YR HD PE	
	background				
Amsterdam	traffic			YR	
	background				
	industrial				
	background				
Ljubljana	background	HD PE			HD
Sosnowiec	traffic	YR HD PE	YR	YR	
	background	YR HD PE			
Aveiro region	traffic	HD PE			
	background	HD PE			
	industrial	HD PE			
Liguria region	traffic			YR HD PE	
	background			YR	HD PE
	industrial			YR	

631 PM₁₀ is classified as a critical pollutant, according to the established
632 criteria, in Sosnowiec, followed by Ljubljana and Aveiro. These three cities
633 are facing different levels of severity regarding this pollutant, and thus, the
634 future policies and measures to control this problem require distinct levels of
635 ambition.

636 PM_{2.5} is highlighted as a serious issue only in Sosnowiec. Nevertheless,
637 besides the spatial limitations of the stations monitoring PM_{2.5}, together
638 with the limited available measurements, there is also time-drawbacks due
639 to the fact that several air quality stations have only started to monitor PM_{2.5}
640 concentrations in the recent years. Additionally, the AQD only sets annual
641 thresholds for PM_{2.5}, and there is no criteria to assess short-term pollution
642 for this pollutant. However, PM₁₀ is only highlighted as a problem in Aveiro
643 region and Ljubljana, when considering the HD and PE indicators, and thus
644 if similar indicators were available for PM_{2.5} probably a similar pattern would
645 be found. All these factors may indicate that PM_{2.5} concentrations may be
646 of concern on other cities, together with the fact that all the cities do not
647 met the WHO recommended limit values.

648 Monitored NO₂ concentrations along the 10-years period denote a pollu-
649 tion problem, mainly associated with road-traffic emissions in Bristol, Am-
650 sterdam, Sosnowiec and Liguria. Among those cities, Bristol and Liguria
651 region had the highest number of exceedances to the hourly limit value.

652 Liguria presents also a pollution problem for O₃ concentration, as well
653 as Ljubljana. In addition, both cities present an increasing trend for the
654 10-years period.

655 It is of note the limitations of this analysis associated with the spatial
656 representativeness of the available measurements, since each city/region has
657 a very different number of air quality stations with valid measurements, and
658 therefore a city with a greater number of stations, may potentially have
659 more air pollution issues highlighted by the available measurements. While
660 no measurements available may hide some important air pollution problems.

661 The pollution problems identified for each case study are independent on
662 the type of station, except in Liguria region where the traffic stations indicate
663 issues related with exceedances to the annual mean of NO₂ concentrations,
664 together with exceedances to the hourly limit, as well as the existence of
665 persistent episodes, while the background and industrial stations highlight a
666 problem of exceedances only to the annual limit.

667 4. Conclusions

668 This work aimed to assess the air quality status of six European cities for
669 the period from 2008 to 2017, identifying the main and common air quality
670 challenges between these different cities/ regions, and its main priorities in
671 terms of pollutants and mitigation strategies. The specific context of the dif-
672 ferent regions and cities of Europe and their complex systems dynamics are
673 considered in this analysis. The results are discussed considering the hourly,
674 daily and seasonal variation of concentrations; a trend analysis providing the
675 evolution during the 10-years period; and the number of persistent air pol-
676 lution episodes, followed by the fulfillment of the EU legislated limit values,
677 together with the stricter, but still voluntary, WHO guideline values.

678 Each city/ region faces different issues and causes of air pollution, but all
679 these case studies have been working on to improve their air quality. In Bris-
680 trol there have been strong downward trends in many air pollutants, but the
681 levels of NO_2 remain persistently high, with transport as the key contributor.
682 PM on the other hand is not widely monitored in Bristol, but background
683 levels are under limit values. Similarly, the main sources of air pollution
684 in Amsterdam are traffic, for NO_2 . Decreasing concentration levels point
685 to some success of Amsterdam air quality policies in recent years. PM_{10}
686 exceedances are a seasonal pollution problem in Ljubljana, with the main
687 particulate matter sources attributed to residential heating, which is still
688 significantly outdated in some parts of the city, where households still heat
689 with burning wood and biomass during winter (Slingerland et al., 2018b).
690 The most pressing issue for air quality within Sosnowiec is particulate mat-
691 ter (PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$), linked with the use of inefficient heating systems,
692 together with poor quality fuels, in winter (Slingerland and Smith, 2018).
693 On the other hand, NO_2 limit values are also exceeded in Sosnowiec. Air
694 quality in the Aveiro region is relatively good, due to an overall relatively
695 low population density in the region, and an open landscape in a maritime
696 climate. PM_{10} (particularly exceedances to the EU daily limit value) and
697 O_3 exceedances do occur occasionally. Wood burning for residential heating
698 and industrial activities are important contributors to air polluting emissions
699 (Slingerland et al., 2018a). Exceedances of NO_2 and O_3 concentrations are
700 still problematic in Liguria region, with road transport, industrial plants and
701 port activities being the main contributors to these problems.

702 Sosnowiec is the only city presenting no compliance with the EU AQ
703 objectives for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations, considering the reduced measurements

704 available in each case study and their potential lack of spatial representative-
705 ness of the entire study areas. However, assuming a transition towards the
706 establishment of the WHO stricter, but still voluntary, guideline values, as
707 the formal EU legal limits, the cities and regions will move to an overall sit-
708 uation of no compliance with the EU legislation, exception made for Liguria
709 Region. Therefore, monitoring networks, particularly the stations measuring
710 PM_{2.5}, should be designed to consider the optimum data that it can generate
711 for public health purpose, and not only for compliance with the AQD.

712 Nowadays, in European urban areas, the current levels of atmospheric
713 emissions, the growing of epidemiological evidence on the health effects of air
714 pollution, the threat of fines by the European Commission towards Member
715 States and the high-profile court cases taken forward by distinct organiza-
716 tions against Member States Governments has raise the media and political
717 profile of air pollution. Together with a recent growth of citizens' sciences
718 activities, where citizens are measuring air quality by themselves. Recently,
719 low-cost sensors were made available to everyone, which implies that every
720 citizen in any city will be able to monitor air quality levels in the surround-
721 ings of their home, or their work place, or any other place. This democratic
722 access to monitoring devices could contribute to strengthen air quality man-
723 agement practices, also considering data from citizen science. Nevertheless,
724 this will require from local stakeholders, decision- and policy-makers a strong
725 investment on training to provide citizens with the required knowledge to
726 understand what they are measuring. In summary, the methodology we pro-
727 pose in this paper represents an useful approach, which could support any
728 local stakeholder, decision- and policy-maker to start processes of citizens'
729 engagement in their city or region. The fact that we use data available on
730 the European database allows everyone to have access to data to reproduce
731 a similar analysis to any European city, and which could be adapted and
732 adopted by any global city.

733 The main findings of this paper highlight the overall decreasing trends of
734 most of the analyzed pollutants during the past decade. These achievements
735 were possible due to a set of air quality policies technological-centered, which
736 have been implemented in Europe, and in each case study, during the last
737 decades. On the other hand, a considerable number of implemented poli-
738 cies were not followed by stronger improvements on air quality and there is
739 still severe air pollution problems within the European regions and cities,
740 as highlighted by the main findings of this study. In addition, most of the
741 identified air pollution problems over the case studies have a strong link with

742 citizens' daily behaviour, practices and activities. Therefore, air quality poli-
743 cies aiming to reduce air pollutant emissions further should focus on changing
744 individual and societal behaviour in parallel with technological changes. Peo-
745 ple and their behaviour need to be included in the way air quality is managed
746 and communicated. This assessment provides a basis to better understand
747 the role of citizens behaviour in the generation of pollution allowing for a
748 realignment of policy process to go beyond the traditional techno-centric
749 approaches to manage air quality.

750 The air quality assessment provided in this paper should be the first
751 step of a citizens engagement process. With this data analysis, citizens will
752 start to understand their recent historical air quality, from the past decade.
753 Therefore, this paper presents a comprehensive methodology suited for any
754 air quality assessment that may be performed for any city, taking advantage
755 of the data available from the official air quality monitoring networks, and
756 using this data to inform citizens. Therefore, the answer to the research
757 question which motivated this paper is that it is possible to support air
758 quality management with a citizen-centered approach through a historical
759 air quality assessment study, and vice-versa, it is essential to support citizen-
760 centered approaches with historical air quality information. The knowledge
761 on the recent historical air quality levels, through a systematic approach, will
762 be a key contribution to improved air quality city policies in the future, as
763 policies, not only local, but also national and European policies, to date have
764 failed to successfully engage citizens because, unlike technological solutions,
765 people and their behaviour are not obviously present in the way that air
766 quality is managed and communicated.

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1017 **5. Supplementary Material**

1018 *5.1. Description of the six EU case studies*

1019 *5.1.1. Bristol, UK*

1020 Bristol is located in the South West of England with a population around
1021 450,000 and an area of 110 km², resulting in a population density around 4000
1022 hab/km². The population was found to be mainly concentrated in the central
1023 area of the considered domain. Bristol's economy is highly service based,
1024 although the industrial sector is still strong. The education sector plays a
1025 major role in the economy of the city (Smith et al., 2017). The climate is
1026 Temperate Oceanic (Cfb), classified by the Köppen-Geiger Climate Classification
1027 System (Peel et al., 2007). The Department for Environment Food &
1028 Rural Affairs is the government department responsible for safeguarding the
1029 natural environment over the UK. The AURN is the UK's largest automatic
1030 monitoring network and is the main network used for compliance reporting
1031 against the AQD. In this paper, the dimensions of the study area for Bristol
1032 are 20 km by 20 km, and so there is only one urban background station
1033 located in the city. In addition, as part of the Local Air Quality Manage-
1034 ment duties, Bristol City Council measures some air quality concentrations
1035 in the city, at five continuous analyser sites: an urban background site, and
1036 the remaining mainly influenced by road traffic. The local authority stations
1037 monitor only Nitric Oxide (NO), Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x) and NO₂ (Smith
1038 et al., 2017). For the considered stations in Bristol the number of stations
1039 per 100,000 inhabitants is 1.3. The location of AQS is presented in Figure
1040 1a). Furthermore, an extensive passive diffusion tube network is used for
1041 indicative monitoring of NO₂.

1042 *5.1.2. Amsterdam, Netherlands*

1043 Amsterdam is the capital of the Netherlands and is in the western part of
1044 the country, in the province of North Holland. Amsterdam is the most pop-
1045 ulous city of the Netherlands with a total population of 834,713 inhabitants
1046 and a high population density around 4700 hab/km². Amsterdam's economy
1047 is strongly influenced by the harbour, the airport, tourism, the creative in-
1048 dustries, and financial and business services (Slingerland et al., 2017). The
1049 population was found to be mainly concentrated in the central area of the
1050 considered domain. Amsterdam has a Temperate Oceanic climate (Cfb), fol-
1051 lowing the Köppen-Geiger Climate Classification System (Peel et al., 2007).

1052 The Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment is re-
1053 sponsible for the air quality monitoring and assessment. In this paper, the
1054 dimensions of the study area are 25 km by 20km, where it exists a vast moni-
1055 toring network with 17 monitoring stations, 6 of which are classified as urban
1056 traffic, 2 urban industrial, 6 urban background and 3 rural background. For
1057 the considered stations in Amsterdam the number of stations per 100,000
1058 inhabitants is 2, the highest of the six cases. The location of these AQS is
1059 presented in Figure 1b.

1060 *5.1.3. Ljubljana, Slovenia*

1061 Ljubljana is the capital and it is located in the central part of Slove-
1062 nia. The city, with an area of 275 km², has a total population of 288,919
1063 inhabitants, with a population density around 1075 hab/km². In Ljubljana
1064 industry, services and tourism are the main further dynamic sectors gener-
1065 ating employment and economic activity (Slingerland et al., 2018b). The
1066 population was found to be mainly concentrated in the central area of the
1067 domain. Ljubljana’s climate is classified, by Köppen-Geiger Climate Classi-
1068 fication System, as a warm-summer humid continental climate (Dfb) (Peel
1069 et al., 2007). In Slovenia, the Environmental Agency of the Republic of
1070 Slovenia is responsible for the air quality protection, in terms of monitoring
1071 of the outdoor air quality, collecting emission data and performing adminis-
1072 tration procedures for air quality protection. In this paper, the dimensions
1073 of the study area are 20 km by 20km, which covers the urban area of Ljubl-
1074 jana where two urban background stations exist, belonging to the national
1075 automatic air pollution monitoring network. For the considered stations in
1076 Ljubljana the number of stations per 100,000 inhabitants is 0.7, the lowest
1077 of the six cases. The location of the AQS is presented in Figure 1c.

1078 *5.1.4. Sosnowiec, Poland*

1079 Sosnowiec is in the southern part of Poland. The city has a total popula-
1080 tion around 206,000 and an area of 91 km², resulting in a population density
1081 around 2376 hab/km². In Sosnowiec, similar to the whole Silesian region,
1082 industry plays the major role in the economic sector. Although, a transition
1083 to a more service-oriented economy can be noticed in recent years (Slinger-
1084 land and Smith, 2018). For the considered domain the population was found
1085 to be more equally distributed. The climate is classified, by Köppen-Geiger
1086 Climate Classification System, as a warm-summer humid continental climate
1087 (Dfb) (Peel et al., 2007). In Poland, the air quality monitoring system is set

1088 under the State Environmental Monitoring established by the Inspection of
1089 Environmental Protection since 1991. In this paper, the dimensions of the
1090 study area in Sosnowiec are 20 km by 20km, which covers 2 monitoring sta-
1091 tions, of which one is influenced by traffic and the other is classified as urban
1092 background. For the considered stations in Sosnowiec the number of stations
1093 per 100,000 inhabitants is 1. The location of the AQS within the study area
1094 is presented in Figure 1d.

1095 *5.1.5. Aveiro region, Portugal*

1096 The Aveiro region is in the central part of Portugal, over the coastal line,
1097 with a total population of 370,394. The Region consists of 11 municipali-
1098 ties, namely Águeda, Albergaria-a-Velha, Anadia, Aveiro, Estarreja, Ílhavo,
1099 Murtoza, Oliveira do Bairro, Ovar, Sever do Vouga and Vagos. The Aveiro
1100 Region has a total area of 1,693 km² resulting in a population density of
1101 218.1 hab/km², being Aveiro, Ovar and Águeda the most populated munic-
1102 ipalities. In the region, industry represents a major part of the economy of
1103 the region, while the port also has an important role, followed by tourism
1104 and services. Agriculture plays a prominent role mainly in the inland parts
1105 of the region (Slingerland et al., 2018a). The region’s climate is classified, by
1106 Köppen-Geiger Climate Classification System, as a warm-summer mediter-
1107 ranean climate (Csb) (Peel et al., 2007). In this paper, the dimensions of the
1108 study area for the Aveiro region are 40 km by 55km. Within the region there
1109 are three AQS managed by the Regional Coordination and Development
1110 Commission of the Center, namely: (i) Aveiro (urban traffic); (ii) Ílhavo,
1111 (suburban background); and (iii) Estarreja, (suburban industrial). For the
1112 considered stations in Aveiro Region the number of stations per 100,000 in-
1113 habitants is 0.8. The location of the AQS is presented in Figure 1e.

1114 *5.1.6. Liguria region, Italy*

1115 Genoa is the capital of the Liguria region located on the north-west of
1116 Italy. The metropolitan area of Genoa is the biggest province of the Lig-
1117 uria region, with an area of 1,838 km² and a total of 855,834 inhabitants in
1118 2011 (population density of 465.5 hab/km²). The strongest economic sectors
1119 in Liguria are services (mainly tourism), and then industry. The Port of
1120 Genoa is also a key local and regional source of income (Artola and Bolscher,
1121 2018). The population is mainly concentrated in the coast. The region
1122 has a hot-summer mediterranean climate (Csa) in the Köppen-Geiger Cli-
1123 mate Classification System (Peel et al., 2007). The Regional Agency for the

1124 Protection of the Ligurian Environment is responsible for the environmental
1125 matters in the Liguria Region. Being responsible for the planning, protection
1126 and management of the environment and nature. In this paper, the dimen-
1127 sions of the study area for this region are 25 km by 15km, which includes
1128 a vast air quality monitoring network distributed over the study area, with
1129 5 urban traffic, 1 urban industrial and 3 urban background stations. For
1130 the considered stations in Liguria Region the number of stations per 100,000
1131 inhabitants is 1.1. The location of the AQS is presented in Figure 1f.

1132 *5.2. Legislation fulfilment*

1133 The following figures show the annual mean values for PM10, PM2.5,
1134 NO₂, and O₃, together with the exceedances observed for the daily limit
1135 value established for PM10 concentrations, the hourly limit value established
1136 for NO₂ concentrations, and the O₃ target value for the protection of human
1137 health, for all the 6 case studies. The comparison between the measurements
1138 in the monitoring stations and the EU objectives allows the characterization
1139 of the air quality status in each ClairCity Pilot. The WHO guideline values
1140 were also considered, since the authors believe that the current legislation
1141 could be updated to be aligned with these more strict guidelines. In the
1142 figures below, the color of each bar represent the classification type of the
1143 stations (e.g. blue for the urban background, green for the suburban back-
1144 ground, yellow for the urban traffic, grey for the urban industrial and orange
1145 for the rural background).

1146 *5.2.1. PM10 concentrations*

1147 Figures S1, S2 and S3 show the annual mean concentrations, the ex-
1148 ceedances observed for the EU daily limit value and the distribution per
1149 month of these exceedances, respectively, for PM10, for all the 6 case stud-
1150 ies.

1151 Bristol has only one urban background station measuring PM10 concen-
1152 trations. This background station has recorded no exceedances to the yearly
1153 EU limit value, and two exceedances to the yearly guideline value from the
1154 WHO (in 2008 and 2010; the records have only slightly exceeded the guide-
1155 line value). The minimum value (of 15.4 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) of PM10 annual mean
1156 concentrations was measured in 2015, while the highest was recorded in 2008
1157 (Figure S1a). The station also recorded exceedances for the PM10 EU daily
1158 mean limit value, but never more than 35 days per year. 2008 was the year
1159 with the highest number of days with exceedances (Figure S2a).

Figure S1: PM10 annual mean concentrations, from 2008 till 2017, for the 6 case studies. The dashed line represents the WHO air quality guideline value, while the solid line represents the PM10 yearly EU limit value for the protection of human health, as defined by the Directive 2008/50/EC.

1160 Amsterdam is the ClairCity pilot city with the greatest number of stations
 1161 monitoring PM10 concentrations, with a set of 9 air quality stations
 1162 with valid records, since 2012 until 2017 (3 traffic, 2 urban background, 3
 1163 rural background, and an urban industrial stations). In addition, there is
 1164 an urban industrial station with valid records that has started to measure
 1165 in 2013 till 2017, and an urban traffic station with valid records from 2008
 1166 until 2016. All the monitoring sites within the study area of Amsterdam
 1167 have monitored PM10 annual mean concentrations in compliance with the
 1168 PM10 yearly EU limit value. While when considering the stricter, but still
 1169 not mandatory, WHO guidelines, the urban traffic stations tend to be above
 1170 the yearly guideline value, exception for the station NL00017 in 2016. Par-
 1171 ticularly, the urban traffic stations are the ones registering the highest PM10
 1172 annual mean concentrations (Figure S1b). Regarding the exceedances for the
 1173 PM10 EU daily mean limit value, the 35 allowed days were only surpassed

Figure S2: Number of exceedances registered for PM10 daily mean limit value for the protection of human health, registered per calendar year from 2008 till 2017, for the 6 case studies. The solid line represents the number of exceedances of 35 allowed per year, as defined by the Directive 2008/50/EC.

1174 in a urban traffic station in 2011. Although, there is days with exceedances
 1175 in multiple other stations (Figure S2b).

1176 Ljubljana has two air quality stations classified as urban background stations
 1177 with valid data (station SI0003A recorded valid measurements from
 1178 2008 to 2011, while the station SI0058A started to have valid measurements
 1179 in 2013 until 2017). The measurements from both stations point out compli-
 1180 ance with the yearly EU limit value during the entire analysis period.
 1181 However, annual mean concentrations are always above the WHO yearly
 1182 guideline value. PM10 annual mean concentrations are lower in the more re-
 1183 cent five years (Figure S1c). Exceedances for the EU daily mean limit value
 1184 were recorded on more than 35 days per year in 2008, 2010, 2011, and 2016
 1185 (Figure S2c).

Figure S3: Monthly distribution of the days where PM10 concentrations above the threshold for the protection of human health were observed in at least one monitoring station in each case study, from 2008 till 2017.

1186 Despite the reduced number of air quality stations available within the
 1187 study area, together with the lack of data before 2010, Sosnowiec is the city
 1188 with the most critical PM10 pollution problem. The urban traffic station,
 1189 which had valid measurements from 2013 till 2017, had registered annual
 1190 mean concentrations always above the yearly EU limit value. While the
 1191 urban background station (valid measurements from 2011 till 2017), had
 1192 recorded PM10 annual mean concentrations above the yearly EU limit value
 1193 between 2011 and 2013, and again in 2017 (Figure S1d). Similarly, both
 1194 stations have exceeded the EU daily mean limit value on more than 35 days
 1195 per year, in all the years with valid measurements. The highest number of
 1196 120 days with exceedances was recorded in the traffic station in 2013, while
 1197 127 days with exceedances were recorded in the background station in 2011
 1198 (Figure S2d).

1199 In Aveiro Region there are only three stations monitoring PM10 con-
 1200 centrations, despite being the larger study area. In this Region, the PM10
 1201 annual mean concentrations are compliant with the yearly EU limit value,
 1202 except the exceedance registered in 2011 on the traffic station. However,
 1203 the annual mean concentrations are always above the WHO guideline value,

1204 except for one of the stations in 2016 (Figure S1e). The industrial station
1205 exceeded the EU daily mean limit value on more than 35 days in 4 years,
1206 while the traffic station exceeded this limit on more than 35 days in 5 years.
1207 The suburban background station exceeded the daily limit value on more
1208 than 35 days in 2011, and 2012 (Figure S2e). Despite the compliance with
1209 the yearly EU limit value, all the three stations registered exceedances for
1210 the PM10 EU daily mean limit value, during the entire period, except the
1211 urban traffic station in 2010. This indicates a problem of PM10 pollution,
1212 mainly associated with episodes, detailed in subsection 3.2.

1213 In Liguria Region, only two out of the nine air quality stations available
1214 have valid measurements for PM10 concentrations, an urban background
1215 station and an urban industrial station. Both stations comply with the yearly
1216 EU limit value, for the entire period. However, the PM10 annual mean
1217 concentrations are above the WHO yearly guideline value in 2014 and 2015
1218 on the background station, and between 2013 and 2015 on the industrial
1219 station (Figure S1f). The EU daily mean limit value was not exceeded on
1220 more than 35 days per year in either station (Figure S2f).

1221 *5.2.2. PM2.5 concentrations*

1222 Figure S4 shows the annual mean PM2.5 concentrations, for all the 6 case
1223 studies.

1224 The urban background in Bristol is the only station measuring PM2.5
1225 concentrations, within the study area, with valid measurements only during
1226 half of the analysis period. In Amsterdam, there are eight air quality stations
1227 monitoring PM2.5 concentrations, all of them with valid records also only
1228 during half of the analysis period. In Ljubljana, one of the urban background
1229 stations is measuring PM2.5 concentrations, while within the Aveiro Region,
1230 the suburban industrial station was monitoring PM2.5 concentrations. In
1231 all these four cities/ regions (Figures S4a, S4b, S4c and S4e), PM2.5 annual
1232 mean concentrations were compliant with the yearly EU limit value, but
1233 exceeding the yearly guideline value from the WHO in all the years and
1234 stations with valid measurements.

1235 The urban traffic station in Sosnowiec is measuring PM2.5 annual mean
1236 concentrations exceeding the yearly EU limit value, and thus exceeding also
1237 the yearly guideline value from the WHO (Figure S4d). On contrary, in Lig-
1238 uria Region the urban background station monitoring PM2.5 concentrations,
1239 from 2013 till 2016, indicates compliance with the yearly EU limit value in all
1240 the years. The measurements were also compliant with the yearly guideline

Figure S4: PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations, from 2008 till 2017, for the 6 case studies. The dashed line represents the WHO air quality guideline value, while the solid line represents the PM_{2.5} yearly EU limit value for the protection of human health, as defined by the Directive 2008/50/EC.

1241 value from the WHO in 2013 and 2014, and only slightly above the guideline
 1242 value for 2015 and 2016 (Figure S4f).

1243 5.2.3. NO₂ concentrations

1244 Figures S5, S6 and S7 show the annual mean concentrations, number of
 1245 exceedances registered for EU hourly limit value for the protection of human
 1246 health and the distribution per month of these exceedances, respectively, for
 1247 NO₂, for all the 6 case studies.

1248 The urban background station from the national monitoring network in
 1249 Bristol, together with five additional automatic stations (an urban back-
 1250 ground and four traffic stations from the local authority), are measuring
 1251 NO₂ concentrations, within the study area. The NO₂ annual mean concen-
 1252 trations monitored by the two background stations are compliant with the

Figure S5: NO₂ annual mean concentrations, from 2008 till 2017, for the 6 case studies. The solid line represents the NO₂ yearly EU limit value for the protection of human health, as defined by the Directive 2008/50/EC.

1253 yearly EU limit value during the entire period (Figure S5a). These back-
 1254 ground stations have only recorded each an exceedance of the EU hourly
 1255 limit value for the NO₂ concentrations (Figure S6a). On contrary, the traffic
 1256 stations often indicate situations of no compliance with the legislated limit
 1257 values. Particularly, the Rupert Street station, which is located on a busy
 1258 traffic thoroughfare in the city centre, is exceeding the yearly EU limit value
 1259 in all the years with valid measurements. This station is also exceeding the
 1260 EU hourly limit value always on more than eighteen times a calendar year,
 1261 with the highest number of 284 days in 2008. The three remaining traffic
 1262 stations are often no compliant with the yearly limit value ³, while they tend

³Fishponds Road station records 4 out of 8, Parson Street School station records 9 out of 10, and Wells Road station records 7 out of 10 years exceeding the yearly limit value.

Figure S6: Number of exceedances registered for NO₂ hourly limit value for the protection of human health, registered per calendar year from 2008 till 2017, for the 6 case studies. The solid line represents the number of exceedances allowed per year, as defined by the Directive 2008/50/EC.

1263 to be compliant with the hourly limit value, with only a few acute situations
 1264 (e.g. in 2018 the Parson Street School station exceeded on 16 days the limit
 1265 value; while the Wells Road station recorded 15 and 17 days exceeding this
 1266 limit in 2008 and 2013, respectively). In addition, an existing network of
 1267 NO₂ diffusive samplers distributed over the urban area is used for indicative
 1268 monitoring of ambient nitrogen dioxide in the city. An analysis of these mea-
 1269 surements indicates NO₂ exceedances to the yearly EU limit value, denoting
 1270 traffic-related NO₂ pollution.

1271 Amsterdam has valid measurements of NO₂ concentrations in five urban
 1272 traffic stations, and five urban background stations for the 10-years period.
 1273 In addition, one rural background and an urban industrial stations have valid
 1274 measurements from 2009 till 2017. All the five urban background stations,

Figure S7: Monthly distribution of the hours where NO₂ concentrations above the threshold for the protection of human health were observed in at least one monitoring station in each case study, from 2008 till 2017.

1275 together with the rural background and the urban industrial stations, are
 1276 compliant with the yearly EU limit value during the entire period. On con-
 1277 trary, three of the traffic stations are not compliant with the yearly EU limit
 1278 value for all the period, while the remaining two traffic stations are not com-
 1279 pliant with the yearly EU limit value only from 2008 till 2012 (Figure S5b).
 1280 Despite few exceedances, all the stations in Amsterdam are compliant with
 1281 the EU air quality objectives, which establishes the limit value of 200 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$
 1282 for NO₂ concentrations not to be exceeded on more than eighteen times a
 1283 calendar year (Figure S6b).

1284 In Ljubljana, there are only valid measurements in one of the urban back-
 1285 ground stations, where NO₂ annual mean concentrations are fully compliant
 1286 with the yearly EU limit value during the entire period (Figure S5c). In
 1287 addition, this station has recorded no exceedances of the EU hourly limit
 1288 value.

1289 In Sosnowiec, the NO₂ annual mean concentrations measured in the ur-
 1290 ban background station are compliant with the yearly EU limit value for all
 1291 the 5 years with valid data. While, in the traffic station, the NO₂ annual
 1292 mean concentrations are exceeding the EU limit value in all the 6 years with

1293 valid data (Figure S5d). In addition, the urban traffic station has recorded
1294 exceedances of the EU hourly limit value, always on more than eighteen times
1295 a calendar year (Figure S6c).

1296 In Aveiro, the NO₂ annual mean concentrations measured in all the three
1297 stations are compliant with the yearly EU limit value for all the years with
1298 valid data (Figure S5e). Furthermore, the background and the industrial
1299 stations are also compliant with the hourly EU limit value. However, the
1300 urban traffic station has recorded few exceedances of the EU hourly limit
1301 value (Figure S6d).

1302 The NO₂ annual mean concentrations measured in all the stations within
1303 the Liguria region are always exceeding the yearly EU limit value for all the
1304 years with valid data (Figure S5f). Two of the traffic stations with valid
1305 data present the highest number of exceedances, greater than the eighteen
1306 exceedances legally allowed (Figure S6e). There are also valid measurements
1307 from an urban industrial station, which are exceeding the EU limit value
1308 in all the 8 years with valid data. This industrial station measure also few
1309 exceedances of the EU hourly limit value, but still compliant. The two urban
1310 background stations were compliant with the yearly EU limit value, except
1311 for the station IT0854A, which has no compliance in 2008 and 2015. These
1312 urban background stations have recorded no exceedances of the EU hourly
1313 limit value for the NO₂ concentrations.

1314 5.2.4. O₃ concentrations

1315 Figure S8 shows the number of exceedances registered for O₃ target value
1316 for the protection of human health, registered per calendar year from 2008
1317 till 2017. The WHO guideline value for O₃ (100 µg.m⁻³) is not displayed
1318 in this figure since it is calculated from eight-hour mean concentrations, a
1319 different metric from the one used by EU legislation. Figure S9 indicates the
1320 distribution per month of those days of exceedance for O₃.

1321 The background station in Bristol registered few exceedances to the O₃
1322 target value almost every year of the 10-years period, with the highest num-
1323 ber of five exceedances registered in 2009. Despite those exceedances, the
1324 background station is always compliant with the 25 exceedance days allowed
1325 per year, averaged over three years (Figure S8a).

1326 Amsterdam recorded lower ozone concentrations in the traffic station, as
1327 expected. Few exceedances to the O₃ target value were registered from 2012
1328 till 2017. Amsterdam was compliant with the 25 days of exceedances allowed
1329 per year (Figure S8b).

Figure S8: Number of exceedances registered for O_3 target value for the protection of human health, registered per calendar year from 2008 till 2017, for five case studies. The solid line represents the number of exceedances allowed per year (averaged over three years), as defined by the Directive 2008/50/EC.

1330 The background station in Ljubljana registered exceedances to the O_3
 1331 target value in all the years, being no compliant with the 25 days of ex-
 1332 ceedances allowed per year from 2011 till 2013, in 2015, and in 2017 (Figure
 1333 S8c).

1334 In Aveiro Region, there are valid measurements of ozone concentrations
 1335 in two air quality stations, a suburban background station, and a suburban
 1336 industrial station. Both stations registered exceedances to the target value in
 1337 all the years with valid data. With the industrial station being no compliant
 1338 with the 25 days of exceedances (Figure S8d).

1339 The stations in Liguria Region recorded exceedances to the O_3 target
 1340 value in all the years with valid data, always greater than the allowed 25
 1341 days of exceedances. These results indicate a problem of no compliance with
 1342 the legislated target value for O_3 concentrations, with more critical numbers

Figure S9: Monthly distribution of the days where O₃ concentrations above the target value for the protection of human health were observed in at least one monitoring station in each case study, from 2008 till 2017.

1343 in 2015 and 2016 (Figure S8e).

1344 *5.3. Persistent episodes during 2008-2017*

1345 The following tables show the complete list of PM₁₀ (Table S1), NO₂ (Ta-
 1346 ble S2), and O₃ (Table S3) persistent episodes, which affected the ClairCity
 1347 case studies between 2008 and 2017. As explained in Section 3.3, in this
 1348 study, an episode is defined as a period of consecutive days (for PM₁₀ and
 1349 O₃) or hours (for NO₂) where a concentration above the threshold was ob-
 1350 served in at least one station of the case study air quality monitoring network.
 1351 An episode is classified as persistent when it lasts for 10 or more consecutive
 1352 days in the case of PM₁₀ and O₃, and for 5 or more consecutive hours in the
 1353 case of NO₂.

Table S1: PM₁₀ episodes that last for 10 or more consecutive days, between 2008 and 2017.

ClairCity Pilot	first hour of exceedance	last hour of exceedance	duration (days)	max concentration ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
Sosnowiec	03/01/2011	13/01/2011	11	150
Sosnowiec	16/02/2011	27/02/2011	12	121
Sosnowiec	27/10/2011	09/11/2011	14	147
Sosnowiec	12/11/2011	26/11/2011	15	192
Sosnowiec	31/01/2012	14/02/2012	15	541
Sosnowiec	12/01/2013	28/01/2013	17	219
Sosnowiec	09/02/2013	21/02/2013	13	98
Sosnowiec	02/10/2013	18/10/2013	17	100
Sosnowiec	12/11/2013	21/11/2013	10	149
Sosnowiec	26/12/2013	04/01/2014	10	114
Sosnowiec	29/01/2014	14/02/2014	17	187
Sosnowiec	24/10/2014	03/11/2014	11	132
Sosnowiec	01/12/2014	10/12/2014	10	155
Sosnowiec	10/02/2015	24/02/2015	15	180
Sosnowiec	23/10/2015	07/11/2015	16	248
Sosnowiec	14/01/2016	24/01/2016	11	143
Sosnowiec	14/01/2017	19/02/2017	37	306
Sosnowiec	21/11/2017	03/12/2017	13	136
Ljubljana	30/01/2011	11/02/2011	13	93
Ljubljana	12/11/2011	22/11/2011	11	102
Ljubljana	18/01/2016	29/01/2016	12	115
Aveiro region	19/01/2008	01/02/2008	14	154
Aveiro region	16/12/2008	26/12/2008	11	163
Aveiro region	08/10/2011	18/10/2011	11	118
Aveiro region	17/12/2011	04/01/2012	19	113
Aveiro region	30/12/2014	13/01/2015	15	121

Table S2: NO₂ episodes that last for 5 or more consecutive hours, between 2008 and 2017.

ClairCity Pilot	first hour of exceedance	last hour of exceedance	duration (days)	max concentration ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
Bristol	16/01/2008 09:00	16/01/2008 15:00	7	236
Bristol	13/02/2008 08:00	13/02/2008 14:00	7	274
Bristol	26/03/2008 14:00	26/03/2008 18:00	5	237
Bristol	02/06/2008 15:00	02/06/2008 19:00	5	243
Bristol	12/10/2008 08:00	12/10/2008 14:00	7	290
Bristol	17/03/2009 15:00	17/03/2009 20:00	6	276
Bristol	18/03/2009 14:00	18/03/2009 21:00	8	287
Bristol	19/03/2009 08:00	19/03/2009 19:00	12	274
Bristol	12/10/2009 16:00	12/10/2009 20:00	5	247
Bristol	06/04/2010 15:00	06/04/2010 19:00	5	247
Bristol	02/06/2012 08:00	02/06/2012 12:00	5	285
Bristol	26/08/2015 14:00	26/08/2015 18:00	5	577
Bristol	27/08/2015 08:00	27/08/2015 19:00	12	310
Bristol	28/08/2015 07:00	28/08/2015 12:00	6	268
Bristol	29/08/2015 10:00	29/08/2015 19:00	10	277
Bristol	18/09/2015 10:00	18/09/2015 16:00	7	268
Bristol	14/10/2015 11:00	14/10/2015 18:00	8	285
Bristol	16/10/2015 15:00	16/10/2015 19:00	5	238
Bristol	20/10/2015 08:00	20/10/2015 16:00	9	280
Liguria region	20/12/2009 17:00	20/12/2009 22:00	6	234
Liguria region	03/12/2012 18:00	03/12/2012 22:00	5	288

Table S3: O₃ episodes that last for 10 or more consecutive days, between 2008 and 2017.

ClairCity Pilot	first hour of exceedance	last hour of exceedance	duration (days)	max concentration ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
Liguria region	23/04/2008	13/05/2008	21	167
Liguria region	28/06/2009	08/07/2009	11	177
Liguria region	19/08/2009	28/08/2009	10	174
Liguria region	08/04/2010	17/04/2010	10	157
Liguria region	01/07/2010	13/07/2010	13	154
Liguria region	17/08/2011	27/08/2011	11	160
Liguria region	18/06/2012	02/07/2012	15	166
Liguria region	04/07/2012	15/07/2012	12	149
Liguria region	25/07/2012	06/08/2012	13	174
Liguria region	14/07/2013	25/07/2013	12	174
Liguria region	10/08/2013	19/08/2013	10	168
Liguria region	15/07/2014	29/07/2014	15	174
Liguria region	13/04/2015	26/04/2015	14	162
Liguria region	08/05/2015	22/05/2015	15	164
Liguria region	24/05/2015	03/06/2015	11	158
Liguria region	06/06/2015	16/06/2015	11	190
Liguria region	18/06/2015	05/07/2015	18	197
Liguria region	31/07/2015	14/08/2015	15	193
Liguria region	02/09/2015	13/09/2015	12	150
Liguria region	18/03/2016	29/03/2016	12	149
Liguria region	09/04/2016	26/04/2016	18	156
Liguria region	14/05/2016	29/05/2016	16	169
Liguria region	20/06/2016	17/09/2016	90	245
Liguria region	19/09/2016	02/10/2016	14	169
Liguria region	18/04/2017	27/04/2017	10	164
Liguria region	25/05/2017	13/06/2017	20	210